

Synthesis of some new thioquinazolinone derivatives of biological activity

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Twenty thioquinazolinone derivatives were prepared by the reaction of ammonium aryldithiocarbamate and appropriately substituted anthranilic acids of which seventeen are new. Their antibacterial and antifungal activities have been evaluated.

Compounds containing quinazolinone ring system exhibit a wide variety of biological activities¹. The present communication reports preparation of some new 2-thioxo-3-aryl-4(3*H*)-quinazolinones (**1**) and evaluation of their biological activities. Many methods of preparation of quinazolinones and thioquinazolinones are reported².

Results and discussion

The structural assignment of **1a-t** is based on their elemental spectral data (IR and ¹H NMR) and by preparation of derivatives. For known compounds literature melting points have also been provided whereas for new compounds elemental analysis are given. The reported melting points of **1a** (lit.³ 91°), **1b** (lit.³ 102°) and **1c** (lit.³ 116°) are unusually low for this type of compounds (*cf.* ref. 4) and are in disagreement with our values. In order to substantiate our data, we also prepared the authentic samples of **1a-c** from the corresponding anthranilic acids and *p*-fluorophenylisothiocyanate by the standard methods⁵. It is observed that not only the melting point values but also the spectral data (IR and ¹H NMR) tally for the compounds **1a-c** prepared by us following the two methods. Thus the samples **1a-c** synthesised by us have the structures proposed. The IR spectral bands indicate the presence of NH, NCS, C=O and C=S groups. The absence of SH band indicates that the compounds exist in the solid state in the thione form which tautomerises to the thiol form in alkaline solution forming the corresponding alkylated derivative **1A**. It lacks IR absorption due to NH stretching of the starting material. The ¹H NMR spectra of the synthesized compound shows a singlet of one NH proton. The 2-dimethylaminoethylthio derivative of the synthesized compounds also support the assigned structure of the compounds **1a-c**.

The antimicrobial screening results indicate that the microorganism *Staphylococcus aureus* is sensitive (zone of inhibition, 11–15 mm) to compounds **1d, e, g, i, m, n, p, r, s**, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* against **1q**, *Citrobacter freundii* and *Providencia vulgaris* against **1i**, *Salmonella typhimurium* against **1e, g, i, p, s**, *Vibrio cholerae* O1 classical against **1e, f, g, i, m, q, r**, *Vibrio parahaemolyticus* against **1g, i**, *Plesimonas shigelloides* against **1e, i**, *Strigella dysenteriae* against **1e, g, i, p, s**, *Escherichia coli* (resistant to all). Compound **1i** is found most active, **1e, g, p** moderately active and **1a-d, h** inactive to almost all the tested microbes. The antifungal screening result indicated *Candida albicans* sensitive towards **1p**, *Aspergillus flavus* towards **1c, d, g, h, p**, *Cryptococcus neoformans* towards **1c, g, i**, *Rizopus* sp. towards **1a, c, d, g, m**, *Penicillium notatum* towards **1s**. Synthesized compounds **1c, g** are most active, **1a, d, h, i, m, p, r, s** moderately active and **1b, e, f, q** are inactive towards the tested fungi.

Experimental

The synthetic approach to these compounds are outlined in Scheme 1. The dithiocarbamate salts were directly condensed with substituted anthranilic acids by refluxing together in absolute ethanol. The reaction involves an initial nucleophilic attack by the amino group of anthranilic acid on ammonium aryldithiocarbamates to form an unstable intermediate *o*-carboxyphenyl thiourea, which then loses a molecule of water to give the quinazolinone ring system.

All m.ps. were recorded by open capillary method and are uncorrected. The progress of the reaction and the purity of the compounds were checked by TLC using silica gel G (E. Merck) plates. IR spectra were recorded on a Jasco FT-IR 5300 spectrophotometer and ¹H NMR spectra on a Jeol FX-90 Q spectrometer (90 MHz) at 27° using TMS as an internal standard. C, H and N were analysed on a Perkin-Elmer analyzer.

	R	X	Y		R	X	Y		R	X	Y
1a	<i>p</i> -F	H	H	1h	<i>o</i> -Cl	Br	H	1o	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	Cl	Cl
1b	<i>p</i> -F	Br	H	1i	<i>o</i> -Cl	Cl	Cl	1p	<i>o</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	H	H
1c	<i>p</i> -F	I	H	1j	<i>o</i> -Cl	I	H	1q	<i>o</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	Br	H
1d	<i>p</i> -F	Cl	Cl	1k	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	H	H	1r	<i>o</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	Br	Br
1e	<i>p</i> -F	I	H	1l	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	Br	Br	1s	<i>o</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	Cl	Cl
1f	<i>o</i> -F	Br	H	1m	<i>m</i> -CH ₃	Cl	Cl	1t	<i>o</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	I	H
1g	<i>o</i> -F	I	H	1n	<i>p</i> -OC ₂ H ₅	Br	Br				

Scheme 1

Ammonium aryldithiocarbamates⁶, 5-bromo- and 3,5-dibromoanthranilic acids⁷, 5-iodoanthranilic acid⁸, and 3,5-dichloroanthranilic acid⁹ were prepared by known methods.

2-Thioxo-3-(4-fluorophenyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinone **1a** :

A mixture of ammonium *p*-fluorophenyldithiocarbamate (3.47 g, 17 mmol) and anthranilic acid (2.06 g, 15 mmol) in absolute ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed on a water-bath for 6 h. The resulting solid was dissolved in minimum volume of alcoholic NaOH solution and reprecipitated with dil. HCl. The solid product was washed with water and recrystallized from ethanol as white crystals (65%), m.p. 310° (Found : C, 61.5; H, 3.6; N, 10.1. C₁₄H₉FN₂OS calcd. for : C, 61.7; H, 3.3; N, 10.3%); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3273, 1684, 1666, 1620, 1535, 1236, 761 cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 7.00–8.66 (8H, m, ArH), 13.39 (1H, s, NH, D₂O exchangeable) ppm.

Other 2-thioxo-3-aryl-4(3H)-quinazolinones **1b–t** were prepared as described above; **1b** (68%), m.p. 325°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3244, 1680, 1614, 1523, 1211, 765 cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 7.13–8.66 (7H, m, ArH), 13.53 (1H, s, NH); **1c** (70%), m.p. 330°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3400, 1680, 1640, 1610, 1580, 1240, 760 cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 7.56–8.66 (6H, m, ArH), 13.50 (1H, br, NH); **1d** (60%), m.p. 175–177°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3420–3300, 1660, 1630, 1590, 1550, 1260, 740 cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 7.02–7.95 (6H, m, ArH), 12.93 (1H, s, NH); **1e** (73%), m.p. 318° (dec.); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3360, 1680, 1660, 1610, 1590, 1250, 775 cm⁻¹; **1f** (62%), m.p. 285°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3380–3220, 1710, 1640, 1600, 1260, 740 cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 7.00–8.50 (7H, m, ArH), 13.48 (1H, s, NH); **1g** (65%), m.p. 173°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3510, 3389, 1674, 1612, 1579, 1543,

1230, 812, 688 cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 6.70–7.83 (7H, m, ArH), 12.50 (1H, br, NH); **1h** (48%), m.p. 290°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3250–3100, 1670, 1620, 1520, 1260, 760 cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 6.90–8.23 (7H, m, ArH), 11.82 (1H, br, NH); **1i** (72%), m.p. 228° (dec.); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3400–3250, 1680, 1630, 1610, 1580, 1250, 740 cm⁻¹; **1j** (70%), m.p. 208°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3400, 1720, 1630, 1600, 1590, 1260, 750 cm⁻¹; **1k** (69%), m.p. 274° (lit.⁴ 276°); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3250, 1720, 1660, 1620, 760 cm⁻¹; **1l** (67%), m.p. 218° (lit.¹⁰ 215°); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3455, 3350, 1680, 1600, 1260, 780 cm⁻¹; **1m** (53%), m.p. 216° (dec.); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3230, 1720, 1660, 1620, 1250, 770 cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 2.40 (3H, s, CH₃), 6.00–7.66 (1H, br, NH), 7.77–8.22 (6H, m, ArH); **1n** (52%), m.p. 220° (lit.¹⁰ 222°); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3440, 3300, 1680, 1620, 1240, 780 cm⁻¹; **1o** (59%), m.p. 204°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3450, 1720, 1650, 1620, 1240 cm⁻¹; **1p** (65%), m.p. 228°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3240, 1700, 1640, 1610, 1240, 750 cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 1.44 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 4.00 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 6.90–8.18 (8H, m, ArH), 12.5 (1H, s, NH); **1q** (60%), m.p. 296°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3258, 1664, 1614, 1523, 1205, 760 cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 1.22 (3H, t, *J* 7 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 3.30 (1H, s, NH), 4.22 (2H, q, *J* 7 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 7.00–8.66 (7H, m, ArH); **1r** (69%), m.p. 220° (dec.); ν_{\max} (nujol) 3380, 3250, 1680, 1620, 1600, 1210, 750 cm⁻¹; δ (DMSO-*d*₆) 1.64 (3H, t, *J* 6 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 4.23 (2H, q, *J* 6 Hz, OCH₂CH₃), 6.70–8.41 (6H, m, ArH), 13.5 (1H, br, NH); **1s** (47%), m.p. 182°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3487, 3371, 1684, 1604, 1543, 1224, 750 cm⁻¹; **1t** (70%), m.p. 290°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 3260, 1730, 1670, 1620, 1200, 780 cm⁻¹.

2-([2-Dimethylamino]ethylthio)-3-(p-fluorophenyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinone **1A** :

A mixture of 2-thioxo-3-(p-fluorophenyl)-4(3H)-quinazolinone (3.9 g, 15 mmol) dissolved in minimum amount of the 10% ethanolic NaOH solution and a solution of 2-dimethylaminoethyl chloride hydrochloride (1.5 g, 15 mmol) in absolute ethanol (10 ml) was stirred for 20 min and the solid product was washed with water and crystallized from ethanol as white crystals (75%), m.p. 320°; ν_{\max} (nujol) 1680, 1670, 1597, 1574, 1504, 1224, 721 cm^{-1} ; δ (CDCl_3) 2.48 (6H, s, $\text{N}(\text{CH}_3)_2$), 2.87–3.13 (4H, m, $\text{SCH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{N}$), 7.00–7.75 (8H, m, ArH).

Antimicrobial¹¹ and antifungal¹² activities of the synthesised compounds were evaluated by reported methods at concentration of 40 $\mu\text{g}/\text{disc}$ against pathogenic bacteria and fungi. Zones of inhibition of the tested microorganisms were compared with that of the control NCTC strain of *E. coil* 10418 and measured using a millimeter rule across the disc.

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References

1. S. F. Queener, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1995, **38**, 4739; B. P. Sharma, *Indian J. Heterocyclic Chem.*, 2002, **11**, 335; R. R. Ruffolo (Jr.) W. Bondinell and J. P. Hieble, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1995, **38**, 3681; D. A. Williams, in "Principles of Medicinal Chemistry", 3rd ed., W. O. Foye, Varghese Publishing House, Bombay, 1989.
2. V. Niementowski, *J. Prakt. Chem.*, 1895, **51**, 564; M. Mckee, R. L. Mckee and R. W. Bost, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1946, **68**, 1902; 1947, **69**, 184, 940; M. T. Bogert and V. J. Chambers, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1905, **27**, 649; 1906, **28**, 207; T. N. Ghosh, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1930, **7**, 981.
3. K. C. Joshi and S. Giri *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1962, **39**, 188.
4. W. L. F. Armarego, in "The Chemistry of Heterocyclic Compounds: Fused Pyrimidines-Quinazolines", eds. A. Weissberger and D. J. Brown, **24** (Part 1), Interscience, New York, 1967, p. 306.
5. J. E. Mac Carty, E. L. Haines and C. A. Vanderwerf, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, **82**, 964.
6. A. I. Vogel, "A Text Book of Practical Organic Chemistry", 4th ed., Longman, London, 1978.
7. A. S. Wheeler and W. H. Oates, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1910, **32**, 770.
8. V. H. Wallingford and P. A. Krueger, *Org. Synth.*, 1943, **2**, 349.
9. T. H. Durrans, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1923, 1424.
10. P. N. Bhargava and M. R. Chaurasia, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1968, **11**, 404.
11. E. J. Stokes and G. L. Ridgeway, "Clinical Bacteriology", 5th ed., Edward Arnold, London, 1980.
12. A. W. Bauer, W. M. M. Kirby, J. C. Sherris and M. Turck, *Am. J. Clin. Pathol.*, 1966, **45**, 493.